

Appendix A Custom search string for each database

Database	Keywords set
ACM	("System of Systems" OR "SoS" OR "System-of-Systems") AND ("software architecture" OR "architecture") AND ("analysis" OR "evaluate" OR "test" OR "review" OR "verification" OR "evaluation" OR "assessing" OR "simulating" OR "trade-offs") AND ("quality" OR "non-functional requirement")
IEEE	("System of Systems" OR "SoS" OR "System-of-Systems") AND ("software architecture" OR "architecture" OR "architecting" OR "architectural") AND ("analysis" OR "evaluate" OR "test" OR "review" OR "verification" OR "evaluation" OR "assessing" OR "simulating" OR "trade-offs")
Scopus	(System of System" OR "SoS" OR "System-of-System") AND ("software architecture" OR "architectural" OR "architecting" OR "archite*") AND ("analysis" OR "evaluate" OR "review" OR "verification" OR "evaluation" OR "assessing" OR "simulating" OR "trade-offs")
Web of Science	TS=("System of Systems" OR "SoS" OR "System-of-Systems") AND TS=("software architecture" OR "architecture" OR "architecting" OR "architectural") AND TS=("analysis" OR "evaluate" OR "test" OR "review" OR "verification" OR "evaluation" OR "assessing" OR "simulating" OR "trade-offs")
Science Direct	("System of Systems" OR "SoS" OR "System-of-Systems") AND ("software architecture" OR "architecture" OR "architecting" OR "architectural") AND ("analysis" OR "evaluate" OR "test" OR "review" OR "verification" OR "evaluation" OR "assessing" OR "simulating" OR "trade-offs")

Table 1. Search string